

Golden Ratio Realistically and Theoretically

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ABSTRACT:

The cognitive approach is gaining popularity not only in psychology, but also among many physicists. New connections have been established between distant areas of science. This article attempts to explore the relationship between landscape studies based on landscape ecology and aesthetics, which materializes primarily in the arts. Mathematics gives optics for study, and tourism benefits from this. The golden ratio, which was already understood and used by ancient people, appears often in compositions (paintings, statues, musical works, literary works, constructions, etc.) deemed to be attractive, as well as in natural processes. This led to the idea of carrying out mathematical calculations in the field of landscape aesthetics, which is closely related to nature tourism. These formulas allow to determine the presence of the golden ratio in landscapes. For these estimates, two approaches, or aesthetic indicators, have been offered. These factors rank landscapes, making it easier for travelers to choose a place.

Keywords: landscapes, aesthetic indicators, cognitive approach, mathematics.

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INTRODUCTION

Art and mathematics are regarded as two separate fields of study. Mathematics is considered to be a completely dry and austere subject, while art is connected to aesthetics; these two fields are opposites. That being said, both mathematics and high art are products of human awareness that aim to convey both the physical and spiritual realities. Artists use their creations to convey psychological atmosphere while considering structure of reality. In the same way that painting depicts figurative element of concrete thing, mathematicians attempt to derive particular mathematical properties in order to study physical phenomena. There are various connections between painting and mathematics. Mathematical geometry is used to examine forms like points and lines, circles, triangles, cubes, and so on in order to interpret artworks, both figurative and abstract. Likewise mathematics can be used in more concrete direct way to analyze painting. Mathematics and visual arts share common aspects in both form and function. One of such relations is explored as Golden ratio. Similarly, painting can be more directly and concretely analyzed using mathematics. There are similarities between mathematics and visual arts in terms of shape and function. The Golden Ratio is one such relationship that is examined. Similarly, painting can be more directly and concretely analyzed using mathematics. There are similarities between mathematics and visual arts in terms of shape and function. The Golden Ratio is one such relationship that is examined [1,2].

One of the oldest instances of this ratio's application is found in Great Pyramid of Giza, which dates back to circa 2560 BC. The Golden Ratio is defined as proportion that is derived from dividing a line into its "extreme and mean ratio" by Euclid of Alexandria, who lived around 300 BC, in *The Elements*. Johannes Kepler referred to Golden Ratio as "one of two great treasures of geometry" (the other being the Theorem of Pythagoras). Another examples of well known works of Golden ratio are Khufu's Pyramid of Egypt, Parthenon in Athens, Greek sculpture, "Mona Lisa" by Leonardo da Vinci, paintings by Rafael, Shishkin and modern Russian artist Konstantin Vasiljev, music of Beethoven and Mozart. It is considered as strongest and oldest ties between mathematics and visual arts. The

Parthenon in Athens, Greek sculpture, Khufu's Pyramid of Egypt, Leonardo da Vinci's "Mona Lisa," paintings by Rafael, Shishkin, and contemporary Russian artist Konstantin Vasiljev, as well as works of music by Beethoven and Mozart are further well-known examples of Golden Ratio artwork. It is thought to be one of the earliest and strongest connections between mathematics and visual arts [1,2].

Comparing the relationships between objects' parts or describing the harmonious relationships between various elements are better uses for term "proportion." Sculpture, temple, image, symphony, poem, and honestly anything that is or is not connected to the arts can all be compared for beauty. The geometric shapes of square, circle, isosceles triangle, and pyramid are only a few of well-known "formulas of beauty." Most widely accepted standard of beauty, however, is particular mathematical ratio known as Golden ratio, sometimes known as Divine proportion, Golden section, Golden number, or Golden mean [1,2].

LITERATURE REVIEW

Pecking Order Theory

According to the pecking order theory, developed by Myers and Majluf, money flows based on hierarchy. The corporation would instead use internal funding before considering debt and equity financing. Asymmetric information is the theoretical foundation for the pecking order. When one person has access to more or better information than the other, a communication breakdown can occur due to information asymmetry. When corporations use internally generated funding, which comes directly from the firm according to the pecking order theory, it aids in minimizing information asymmetry. Internal financing is the most cost-effective and time-efficient option compared to the costs associated with obtaining external financing, such as debt or equity financing. The pecking order theory says that a corporation considers internally generated funding before considering external funding, such as debt and equity. No percentage was specified in the capital structure concerning debt and equity financing. The golden ratio was used to build on the pecking order theory of the percentage of debt and equity that a corporation can use in its capital structure. The application of the golden ratio indicates that the larger line should be 0.618 and the smaller line should be 0.382; Most firms used a greater percentage of debt financing compared to equity financing. Therefore, in this paper, it was assumed that the debt component in the capital structure should be 0.618 and the equity component should be 0.382 [3,4].

Agency Cost Theory

According to agency theory, managers, shareholders, and debt holders have competing interests. For a corporation to maximize its value, it needs to have the best capital structure, and having the best capital structure reduces agency costs. An agency cost exists between the shareholders, management, and debt and equity holders. Company executives consider their interests initially before considering increasing shareholders' wealth and the stock price for investors because of agency problems. Debt financing is more preferred by managers over equity financing because it costs less to obtain debt and faceless agency problems between the management and shareholders [3].

Market Timing Theory

Market timing theory says that when deciding whether to issue debt or equity, it is important for a corporation to think about how the market value changes over time. It also asserts that the state of the stock market affects management's decisions about capital structure or that managers use information from the stock market when deciding how to finance a business. Managers take advantage of a rising market by issuing new shares of stock or selling overvalued shares, whereas falling markets often prompt them to turn to debt financing instead. According to this theory, opportunities in the capital market happen when people do not have the same amount of influence and information about the choice of a financing strategy. When the market price share drops and corporations consider using debt financing, the golden ratio can guide them to the percentage of debt and equity financing they can use in their capital structure [3].

METHODOLOGY

Considering the various research methods that aim to obtain summarized information about given topic, the method of choice for this paper is integrative review, as it allows an in-depth methodic approach, enabling the integration of experimental and non-experimental studies.

GOLDEN RATIO IN MATHEMATICS

Golden Ration Definition №1

The Golden ratio, $j = 1.61803\dots$ has fascinated people of multiple disciplines, sciences and arts alike, for centuries. The definition involves dividing a line segment into two parts, of lengths A and B , such that the ratio of the larger part, A , to the smaller part, B , equals the ratio of the whole segment to the larger part [5,6].

$$\frac{A}{B} = \frac{A+B}{A}. \quad (1)$$

Figure 1. Golden Ratio Representation №1

The Golden ratio may be defined as a cut to a line (dashed) into lengths A and B , as given in the figure, such that the ratio A/B is equal to the ratio $(A+B)/A$. This definition is an example of self-similarity. This means that the line segment is similar to parts of itself, with A being to $A+B$ what B is to A . If a similar division was to be made to length A , then the larger part of that cut would have length B . The common ratio is the Golden ratio, the exact value of which can be found by setting A/B equal to j to give a quadratic equation [5,6].

$$\phi^2 - \phi - 1 = 0. \quad (2)$$

The positive solution of this quadratic is the Golden ratio,

$$\phi = \frac{1 + \sqrt{5}}{2} = 1.618\,033\,988\,749\,894\,9\dots \quad (3)$$

The other solution gives,

$$\phi = \frac{1 - \sqrt{5}}{2} = -0.618\,033\,988\,749\,894\,9\dots \quad (4)$$

The second solution has the same decimal expansion as the first. An interesting property of the Golden ratio is that its reciprocal can be obtained by subtracting one, i.e. [5,6],

$$\frac{1}{\phi} = \phi - 1 = 0.618\,033\,988\,749\,894\,9\dots \quad (5)$$

Golden Ration Definition №2

Mathematic definition of Golden Ratio: two parts (a and b, a>b) according to the Golden Ratio are in proportion to each other if the whole (a+b) is in proportion to the greater part (a) exactly as the greater part (a) to the smaller (b) [5,6]:

Figure 2. Golden Ratio Representation №2

$$\frac{a+b}{a} = \frac{a}{b} \quad (6)$$

I.e. half the length of the greater part equals the geometrical centre of the length of the sum and the smaller part:

$$a^2 = (a+b) \times b \quad (7)$$

In other words the greater part is in proportion to the smaller part as the smaller part to the difference of the two parts. Pythagoreans regarded the rectangle the most aesthetic the sides of which all meet the Golden Ratio [5,6].

$$\frac{a}{b} = \frac{b}{a-b} \quad (8)$$

that is [5,6]

$$b^2 = a \times (a - b) \quad (9)$$

Figure 3. Golden Rectangle (Pythagoras)

GOLDEN RATIO IN NATURE

Spiral Galaxies

A wide variety of natural phenomena can be linked to the Golden ratio, and these occur on length scales ranging from the atomic to the astronomical. Here, some such phenomena shall be explored, starting at the astronomical scale and progressing to smaller scales. One of such examples can be named Spiral Galaxies [7,8].

The largest length scale on which ϕ has been observed is that of galaxies, which comprise of billions of stars bound by gravity. Many galaxies are characterised by their visually striking spiral arms. A commonly used mathematical model for these arms is the logarithmic spiral, for which the shape remains the same as size increases due to a constant pitch angle [7,8] (Figure 4).

A point, p , on any spiral can be described by its distance r from the centre point, p_0 , and a turn angle, θ . The tightness of a spiral at p is given by the pitch angle, χ , the angle between the centre-to-point vector (dashed line) and the normal to the spiral at p (dash-dotted line). Equivalently, the angle, ψ , to the tangent (dotted line) can be used instead, with $\psi + \chi = \pi / 2$. For a logarithmic spiral, the pitch angle is constant over the whole spiral [7,8] (Figure 5).

Approximation of the Golden spiral, using the Golden rectangle. The rectangle can be split into a square, and a smaller Golden rectangle. Then circular arc lengths can be drawn across the squares, with radius equal to the square length. This means each arc has a different radius, thus the resulting spiral is not logarithmic [7,8].

Figure 4. Golden Spiral Formula Representation

Figure 5. Golden Spiral Representation №2

Leonardo da Vinci Works

Golden Ratio is the basic organising structure for example in the sonatas of Mozart; V. symphony of Beethoven; compositions of Bartók, Kodály, Debussy and Schubert; just like in the Divine Comedy of Dante and the poem of Lajos Kassák entitled: The Horse Dies – the Birds Fly Out. In the arrangement of the most known compositions – e.g. those of Leonardo da Vinci or Michelangelo – Golden Ratio is applied similarly to the parameters of the Hungarian Saint Crown. This approach is also widespread in the works of contemporary painters, to mention only the MAD1 movement and the works of its significant Hungarian representative, János SaxonSzász [7,8] (Figure 6).

The famous Vitruvius Man is also the work of Leonardo da Vinci in which he describes the accurate proportions of the bone structure of a man. He was the first to suggest that the human body is composed of “building stones” the proportion of which is always j [7,8] (Figure 7).

Nature

Most widely known examples from Nature: proportion of one spiral of the nautilus or nautili house to the other is j , i.e. $AC/DB=FG/EG$. Proportion of female bees to male bees in beehive or the proportion of parts of an insect (head-thorax-abdomen) to each other is also j . Similar structure can be detected in a spider web as well [7,8] (Figure 8).

Figure 6. Mona Lisa

Figure 7. Vitruvian Man

Figure 8. Spiral of a Nautilus Shell

Lamellae of the pine-cone and that of the pine apple or the seeds in the sunflower head are placed along two opposite logarithmic spirals where the proportion between the diameter of two neighbouring rows is j . It is also frequent that leaves (phyllotaxis), buds and petals are ordered not symmetrically. Such order composes the onion head of the onion leaves, the cabbage head of the cabbage leaves furthermore the raspberries, roses of the cauliflower and the thorns of certain cactuses are also arranged in this order [7,8].

Figure 9. Phyllotaxis

Similar to the house of the nautili the lithified skeleton of ammonites that lived dominantly in the Palaeozoic and Mesozoic also shows the characteristic logarithmic spiral structure just like most of the galaxies that have spiral structure. Typical cyclones in the Atmosphere also take this form. Flying trajectory of falcons also forms a logarithmic spiral when it approaches its prey watching it in this way always from the same angle [7,8].

Figure 10. Examples of Golden Spiral in Nature

In spite of listing endless numbers of examples I would like to draw attention to the similarity that can be detected in certain phases of growth of living beings both in the world of plants and animals and thus in the case of human beings as well. Based on these images this spiral form seems to be dominant over the development of life as well and deviation from it can be regarded as exception [7,8].

Figure 11. Examples of Spiral Form in Lives Development

CONCLUSION

A remarkable number of apparently disparate natural phenomena can be linked to the Golden ratio, and occurrences of this number may be found at multiple length scales, ranging from the galactic to the atomic. Some of these instances, such as planetary orbits, RR Lyrae stars, phyllotaxis, the ultimatum game, Ising chains and quasicrystals stem from the fact that the Golden ratio is, in sense of Hurwitz's theorem, the most difficult number to approximate using rational quotients. In such cases, the Golden ratio manifests itself through its rational approximants, given by the ratios of successive Fibonacci numbers. In other cases, including spiral galaxy pitch angles, protein and amino acid shape, atomic bond lengths and black holes, the observations or calculations resulting in the Golden ratio appear coincidental, but may also indicate that some deeper, as yet unknown, explanation exists.

The propensity of this number to appear in unexpected places does however, sometimes lead to misconceptions, such as the idea that the nautilus shell and hurricanes are governed by the Golden spiral. Nevertheless, in exploring just one single number, one may encounter a plethora of fascinating topics from variety of disciplines. Whenever the Golden ratio (or nearby value) is encountered in science, there is exciting opportunity for scientific, philosophical and artistic investigations.

REFERENCES

1. A.H. Church, On the relation of Phyllotaxis to Mechanical Laws. Williams and Norgate, London, 462 pp, 1904.
2. J. Kepler, The Six-Cornered Snowflake, 1611.
3. M. Livio, The Golden Ratio: The Story of Phi, the World's Most Astonishing Number. Broadway Books, New York, 320 pp, 2003.
4. C. Stewart, Myers and Nicholas S. Majluf. Journal of Financial Economics, vol. 13, issue 2, pp. 187-221, 1984.

5. L. Pacioli, De Divina Proportione. (On the Divine Proportion). Venice, 1509.
6. L. Pisano, L. Liber Abaci. (Book of Calculation), Rome, Reprint in 2002 by Sigler, L.E., Springer Verlag, Berlin–London, 636 pp, 1202.
7. M. Ghyka, The Geometry of Art and Life; Dover Publications, Inc.: New York, NY, USA, 1977.
8. S. Olsen, The Golden Section: Nature's Greatest Secret; Wooden Books: Glastonbury, UK, 2006.